

STUDIES ON CULM ANATOMY OF GENUS *Cyperus* L. (Cyperaceae)

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Abstract

The genus *Cyperus* L. (Cyperaceae) is the second largest genus in the family, represented by 37 species in Marathwada region (W.Khan 1998). It is extremely polymorphic in exomorphic characters and shows heterogeneous assemblage of ill defined species.

Present paper focused on the anatomical characters of culm (Stem) within the genus which may helpful for delimitation of infra-specific characters within the genus. Author has carried out anatomical studies of some important species of the genus and original observations will be presented at the time of presentation in the conference.

Keywords: *Cyperus*, Culm, Anatomy

Introduction

Cyperaceae is one of the largest and most intricate family and are represented by about 70-80 genera and 4000 species distributed throughout world. In India it has 28 genera and over 500 species. The critical taxonomic study of the family has been neglected by most of the cyperologists due to minute and greatly reduced floral structures.

The genus *Cyperus* L. is second largest genus in the family and consists of about 600 species all over world (Kukenthal 1936). It appears extremely polymorphic in taxonomic status and shows heterogenous assemblage of ill defined species. Taxonomically genus indicates close affinity with other genera like *Juncellus* Kyllinga, *mariscus*, *pycreus* etc.

Clarke (1893) divided cyperus into 7 genera on the basis of number of stigmas, achene position and glumes in a spikelet. Kern (1974) disagree with him and termed the treatment of Clarke as artificial as the genera are ill defined and preferred by giving subgeneric status. Koyama (1961) treated cyperus in a wide sense (including *lipocarpa*) as the taxa possesses Cyprus like embryo. Metcalfe (1971) and many other provided ample anatomical evidences to indicate a close affinity between *Cyperus* and other genera.

In present paper author focused detailed culm anatomy of selected five species of genus *Cyperus* L. these anatomical features support to establish status of morphological variations and to establish infra generic, specific and infraspecific delimitations.

Material And Methods

For anatomical study author collected the five anatomically interesting species of genus *Cyperus* L. by visiting different localities of Marathwada. The specimens were collected and processed and made into herbarium specimens. The fresh material of culm was fixed in FAA. The transections of culm were taken by both free hand and microtome and made into permanent preparation by using differential double staining technique. The microphotographs were taken on the olympus Research microscope without blue filter.

Results**Transverse Section of culm *Cyperus corymbosus* Rottb.**

T.S. of culm is circular in outline, Epidermis : it is outermost single layered of rectangular cells with thick deposition of cutin on its outer wall, it shows few stomata. It is followed by a ground tissues with distinct outer zone made up of compactly arranged parenchymatous cells with abundant chloroplasts. The outer zone shows small vascular bundles surrounded by a single layer of bundle sheath. Each vascular bundle shows 'V' shaped xylem and patch of phloem in between the arms of xylem. The inner ground zone is made up of loosely arranged, thin walled parenchymatous cells with abundant air cavities and few secretory cells. The zone shows large vascular bundles distributed in the parenchymatous cells. The vascular bundles are identical in structure with that of peripheral vascular bundles.

Transverse Section of culm *Cyperus difformis* L.

T.S. of culm appears triangular in outline. Epidermis : it is an outermost single layer of thin walled parenchymatous two sizes of cells, outer walls are suberized. Ground tissue : Chlorenchymatous with abundant irregular large air cavities separated by the columns. Each column shows a strand of sclerid cells at its base lying very close to epidermis. Vascular bundle: vascular bundles many distributed unevenly in the ground tissues. Each vascular bundle has a sheath of radiating chlorenchymatous cells.

Transverse Section of Culm *Cyperus flavidus* Retz.

Culm appears sub-spherical in outline in T.S. epidermis is single layered rectangular cells with thick cuticle. Hypodermis : It is present in the form isolated sclerenchymatous patches. Remaining part is occupied by thin walled translucent cells. Assimilatory tissues : The radiating chlorenchyma are present around the peripheral vascular bundles. Ground tissues : Cells are parenchymatous with abundant small sized vascular bundles on peripheral side and few scattered larger vascular bundles present on inner side, vascular bundles are collateral type. Central ground tissue disappear forming large hallow pith, few isolated secretory cells are found in assimilatory zone.

Transverse Section of Culm *Cyperus iria* L.

Epidermis is a single layer of rectangular cells with outer wall very thick. Hypodermis : it is in the form of isolated patches of sclerenchymatous cells alternating with parenchymatous cells of outer ground tissues. Ground tissues : made up of thin walled parenchymatous loosely arranged cells with abundant air cavities. It shows many vascular bundles distributed unevenly. Each vascular bundle is collateral, surrounded by a sclerenchymatous sheath and a cap of on the inner side. Xylem appears 'V' shaped with a protoxylemic cavity.

Transverse Section of culm *Cyperus rotundus* L.

Culm appears somewhat acutely triangular in T.S. epidermis is single layered with compactly arranged rectangular cells with thick cuticle, stomata present. It is followed by the hypodermis showing isolated, sclerenchymatous patches which are pulviniform to sub-rectangular present at specific intervals through the peripheral region remaining patches show translucent cells. Assimilatory tissue : chlorenchyma present radially around the peripheral young vascular bundles, their cells consist of abundant starch grains and few isolated secretory cells. Ground tissues : The central zone is occupied by thin walled, spongy parenchyma with large intercellular spaces and few isolated secretory cells distributed within the ground tissues. Vascular bundle : The vascular bundles are amphivasal type, surrounded by single sclerenchymatous sheath, large number of young vascular bundle are distributed in the periphery alternating by larger once at certain places in the ground tissues.

Cyperus rotundus L.

Conclusion

From the above investigations it can be concluded that the culm (Stem) anatomy of genus *Cyperus* shows much variability in outer peripheral region than central ground tissues in distribution of Sclerenchyma, vascular bundles, air cavities, chlorenchyma and secretory cells, such anatomical characters support the delimitation of species within the genus.

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